

Order of elemental analysis

*You can bring your samples (min 5 mg) to Sylvie (lab 07) on Mondays and Thursdays **between 9:30am and 11:00am***

Customer

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Sample

Sample name: MAG166	
Aspect / texture: yellow crystalline solid	
Molecular formula: C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄	Molar mass: 374.44
Used solvent: CHCl ₃ , Ethyl acetate, Petroleum ether	
Structure:	

Sample details

Is the sample harmful? (skin, lungs, toxic)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample light sensitive?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample electrostatic?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is the sample hygroscopic?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Do you want your sample back?	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Additional informations:		

Elemental analysis

Sample name: MAG166

Single determination

Double determination

C <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	H <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	N <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Other elements: -		

Results

Analysis number: 2020-130			
Sample name: MAG166			
Expected values:	C 76.99 %	H 5.92 %	N 17.09 %
Results:	C 76.01 % - %	H 6.06% - %	N 0.00% - %
Other elements: -			
Remarks: Analyte contains no Nitrogen.			

Date/Visa operator

16.12.2020, Jonas Zurflüh